

PRINCIPLES OF DIVISION OF WORD CATEGORIES IN UZBEK LANGUAGE

Shodieva Gulrukh Nazir qizi

1st year master of linguistics of Fergana State University

Dona Usmonova,

Head of English language department, Fergana State University

dona.s.usmonova@gmail.com

Annotation: Word categories-groups of words in the language, in which they are distinguished by the presence of a single system of grammatical categories, a specific word variation, forms and types of word declension, the generality of syntactic functions (in some literature they are also called "lexical grammatical categories of words"). Hence, when dividing words into Groups, Categories, it is mainly taken into account the similarity of their syntactic, morphological and spiritual (semantic) properties. In this article, opinions and comments are made about the principles of the division of vocabulary into categories in the Uzbek language.

Keywords: word categories, tasks, basis and principles, independent, auxiliary and separate word categories.

According to the lexical and grammatical similarity of words, some lexical - grammatical groups are called parsing word categories. In addition to their grammatical meanings in the division of words into categories, the lexical meaning is also one of the main signs-the Account Allocation. Words that have both grammatical and lexical meanings and participate in the sentence as an independent syntactic unit are called independent words. To independent words: noun, adjective, number, pronoun, verb, adverb.

Words can also be classified according to the positions they occupy in the sentence. Words that can stand in the same syntactic position in the sentence or

perform the same syntactic task are included in one series of words. In this it is important not only the sum of syntactic functions, but also the degree of uniqueness of each of these functions to a certain category of words. These tasks are divided into primary and secondary types. For example, in the Uzbek language, as in many other languages, words in the category noun and verb can come both in the function of the possessive, and in the function of the cross-section, but the fractional function for verb is the primary, the possessive function is the secondary. Similarly, the possessive function for nouns is primary, and the fractional function is secondary.

It is also worth noting that some independent words in our language can also be transferred to the auxiliary word task, having lost its independent lexical meaning in the process of speech and having become characteristic of a grammatical and semantic expression.

Words that do not have an independent lexical meaning, do not fulfill the function of a sentence fragment, but serve to correlate words and sentences or to add to them additional subtleties of meaning (loading) are called auxiliary words. Auxiliary words will be three different according to the general tasks: 1) Assistant; 2) Connecting; 3) Loading.

And exclamation, imitation and modal words form a separate group of auxiliary words. Because exclamation and imitation words are used both as a sentence fragment and as an independent word-sentence. At the same time, it is also able to participate in the legalization of independent words. But these words are similar to auxiliary words in that they cannot be a term of action and phenomenon, that is, they cannot express a lexical meaning. Therefore, exclamation, imitation, modal words each form a separate category with their own characteristics.

Apparently, when parsing words into categories, first comes from the emphasis on the lexical meaning, secondly, the morphological form, the third, the feature of performing a syntactic task, the fourth, the application of the blockade (distribution). Accordingly, the present group of words in the Uzbek language:

- 1) independent words such as noun, adjective, number, pronoun, verb, adverb;

2) auxiliary words such as auxiliary, connecting, predicate;

3) modal words, imitation words, exclamation words, consisting of a separate group of auxiliary words.

In most of the above classifications, independent and auxiliary word categories are visible. If, although this classification is considered a maternal classification, it has not lost its value even now. In the traditional classification, 6 word categories are included in the word categories, in which the noun category is the primary, and verb is the secondary pole, but in some studies the imitation words are also included in the independent word categories, and the verb word category is carried forward. Verb is the largest in all word categories, rich grammar categories, the perfect word category. However, it is known that when a person comes to the world, he first encounters everything that he has. Any action is performed either by the subject or by the person. Accordingly, the approval to us is a traditional classification.

An independent category of words has a lexical and grammatical meaning, having the property of forming a form with the ability to come up in the task of a part of speech. And the auxiliary words do not have a lexical meaning, they do not change either morphologically, they cannot come in the task of the sentence section and also have a justification feature. And Modal, exclamation and imitation words are not like both independent words and auxiliary words, there are no mutual common aspects. Therefore, a separate word is called a series.

*For example, we use a variety of sample mantas to teach vocabulary to demanding young people. 1-Exercise. Give a description of the grammatical form of **pronouns** used in the following sentences.*

1. In this regard, the material and spiritual condition of the students is extremely chatterbox. (Oybek) in our hearts of all of us. 2. Old moral girls say where (Oybek). 3. Although his yellow satin was pleasing to him, but now he decided to dress up with the fancy of the scallops, without putting his own will (A Kadiri). 4. But although he could not meet anything other than a gap in his perspective, he

would have seen a more glorious meaning (A.Kadiri). 5. From me, if I leave in the same way, a decent person will not quit sucking (Kh. Tuxtaboev)

In the current Uzbek linguistics there are also different views on the study Grammatical categories. Although in traditional linguistics the grammatical categories of each category of words are studied within their own framework, in later times the word-changing tools - consonants in nouns and verbs-personal suffixes are called forms of communication-relations that serve the syntactic connection of words and are studied beyond the word-categories.

*2-exercises. Distinguish words belonging to the category of **adverbs** from the following sentences.*

1. One day, when I entered the goods receipt, I heard a coincidence that Sherkhan was whispering with Said Khalil in the shop in front of the mosque (P.Kadirov). 2. Whatever... he will die! Today, if not today... he will die tomorrow! - said the latter (Togay Murad). 3. Even those who stepped on the heart, soon after, would die from the full (T.Malik). 4. Humor did so deliberately to negate his intentions and laugh over, apparently (P.Kadirov).

In our opinion, it is preferable for each category to be given within its own category of words. Because the fact that each category of speech cannot be studied within its own category of speech causes it to not understand the characteristics of speech categories as a whole and create difficulties in analyzing speech categories. Therefore, it is desirable that each category should be studied within its own framework, dividing into grammatical categories by form-makers and word-changers.

Conclusion. The question of vocabulary has not been studied in a situation that will equally appeal to everyone, although it has been taken as an object in many studies all over the world, including Uzbekistan. Material related to the word of series, information should not be taken from dictionaries. Because they will be included in the dictionaries processed. In our case, all the words in the text and their different grammatical rules can be analyzed in a convenient way.

REFERENCES:

1. Komilova, N. A. (2022, June). COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF LEXICAL VERBALIZERS OF THE CONCEPT "GENDER" IN UZBEK AND ENGLISH LANGUAGES. In *International Scientific and Current Research Conferences* (pp. 103-106).
2. Komilova, N. A. Comparative Analysis of "Gender" Concept and Issues of Gender Field in English and Uzbek Languages.
3. Do'smatov, H. (2022, June). O 'ZBEK TILIDA SO 'Z TURKUMLARI TASNIFI MASALALARI. In *INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE: PROBLEMS AND SCIENTIFIC SOLUTIONS*. (Vol. 1, No. 1, pp. 108-113).
4. Abdilkadimovna, K. N. (2021). Comparative And Linguocultural Analysis Of The Concept" Gender" In Uzbek And English Languages. *The American Journal of Social Science and Education Innovations*, 3(06), 112-117.
5. Мирзаахмедович, Х. Ф., & Комилова, Н. А. (2021). ИНГЛИЗ ВА ЎЗБЕК ТИЛЛАРИДА ГЕНДЕР КОНЦЕПТУАЛ СЕМАНТИКАСИ ВЕРБАЛИЗАТОРЛАРИ НОМИНАТИВ ТУРЛАРИНИНГ ЛИНГВОКУЛЬТУРОЛОГИК ХУСУСИЯТЛАРИ. *МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫЙ ЖУРНАЛ ИСКУССТВО СЛОВА*, 4(6).
6. qizi, S. G. N. ., & qizi, R. M. A. . (2022). Word Categories in English. *Middle European Scientific Bulletin*, 26, 14-16. Retrieved from <https://cejsr.academicjournal.io/index.php/journal/article/view/1431>
7. Shodieva, G. N. Q., & Rakhmonova, M. A. Q. (2021). INFORMATION PERIOD CHANGE OF PEOPLE'S OUTLOOK, NEGATIVE AND POSITIVE IMPACT OF THE INTERNET. *Scientific progress*, 2(8), 563-566.
8. Do'smatov, D., & qizi Shodiyeva, G. N. (2022, May). O 'ZBEK TILSHUNOSLIGIDA SO 'ZLARNI TURKUMLARGA AJRATISH TAMOYILLARI. In *INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCES ON LEARNING AND TEACHING* (Vol. 1, No. 8, pp. 770-774).

9. Shodiyeva, G. N. Q. (2022). MATN GRAMMATIKASINING ASOSIY MUAMMOLARI. *Academic research in educational sciences*, 3(NUU Conference 2), 1173-1176.
10. Kizi, S. G. N., & Tolibovna, S. A. (2022). Semantic features and new methods of non-standard English. *Ta'lim fidoyilari*, 24(17), 2-272.
11. Najmiddinovna, R. Z., & Najmiddinovna, R. K. (2022). INNOVATIVE APPROACHES IN FOREIGN LANGUAGE TEACHING. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCE & INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH ISSN: 2277-3630 Impact factor: 7.429*, 11(05), 19-21.
12. Усмонова, Д. С. (2019). Роль и особенность соматических фразеологизмов различных языков. *Мировая наука*, (9), 250-252.
13. Usmonova, D. S., & Yusupova, M. I. Q. (2021). COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF THE SOMATIC PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS OF THE ENGLISH AND RUSSIAN LANGUAGES WITH THE COMPONENT "HEART". *CURRENT RESEARCH JOURNAL OF PHILOLOGICAL SCIENCES (2767-3758)*, 2(11), 94-99.
14. Usmonova, D., & Jurayev, I. (2021). SEMANTIC CHANGE OF VERB MEANING. *CURRENT RESEARCH JOURNAL OF PHILOLOGICAL SCIENCES (2767-3758)*, 2(11), 150-152.
15. Usmonova, D.S. (2021). Axiological Characteristics Of English, Uzbek And Russian Phraseological Units. *The American Journal of Social Science and Education Innovations*. -IMPACT FACTOR 2021: 5. 857. Published: June 18, 2021 | Pages: 40-45, 2021-yil.